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**Assessment of Heavy Metal Contents of Oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*)
and Associated Health Risks in Rivers State**

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Abstract

The health risks associated with the consumption of Oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*) sourced from three different communities in Rivers State (Bille, Okirika and Abonnema) were investigated. The collected samples were brought to the laboratory and processed further for analysis. The Oyster was scrubbed and cleaned with double distilled water. The soft tissue of each Oyster was brought out from its shell, rinsed with double distilled water and dried in an oven at 700C to a constant weight. The dried sample was acid digested and an aliquot aspirated into an Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (PG instrument AA500) to determine the concentrations of Zn, Cd, Cr, Cu and As which was then used for calculating the health risks accruable from its consumption. The results revealed that these metals were bio-accumulated by the Oyster at a concentration that is lower than the maximal permissible limit by FAO/WHO and showed no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$) at the sourced locations. Health risks analysis revealed that the EDIM and HRI were all less than unity ($EDIM < 1$ and $HRI < 1$) and indicates that no undue health issue may arise by consuming the Oyster. Similarly, the THQ and HI were all below 1 ($THQ < 1$ and $HI < 1$) and implies that there is no possibility of developing non-carcinogenic diseases or systemic problem and health hazard. The overall result has shown that the sourced Oyster can pose no health danger to the population exposed to these metals via consumption.

Keywords: Heavy metal contents, oyster, health risks assessment.